

T6.2 – Public Clean-up events

Technical report of the public beach and sea-bottom clean-up events implemented between June 2024 and March 2026 within the NETTAG+ project across Portugal, Spain, Malta, Croatia, and Italy. The activities combined large-scale clean-ups with public engagement to raise awareness of the extent and diversity of marine litter and to promote more responsible consumption and waste management practices. Involving fishers, recreational divers, schools, and local communities, the events provided hands-on experience of marine pollution and reinforced shared responsibility for protecting marine ecosystems.

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Summary NETTAG+ Project

NETTAG+ aims to provide a portfolio of three innovative smart and sustainable solutions to address the negative impacts of abandoned, lost or otherwise discarded fishing gear (ALDFG) on marine life and habitats. NETTAG+ will be based on synergistic activities between the fisheries industry, scientists and NGOs to develop three solutions to PREVENT, AVOID and MITIGATE the harmful impacts of ALDFG.

NETTAG+ will PREVENT marine litter derived from fisheries activities, AVOID loss of fishing gears, and MITIGATE harmful impact by removing existing ALDFG. These three solutions will jointly contribute to reduce ALDFG and marine pollution, namely by: reducing the introduction of hazardous chemicals and microplastics originating from ALDFG; reducing ghost fishing, bycatch and entanglements of sensitive or endangered species on ALDFG; and improving mapping, tracking and recovery technologies to retrieve ALDFG.

NETTAG+ aims to upgrade and upscale the integrative preventive approach that started in the previous NetTag project, and aims to replicate it in Mediterranean regions, providing the fisheries industry with three smart and environmentally-friendly solutions to reduce ALDFG and prevent the environmental impacts of fishing gears. The three solutions will be developed to maturity (TRL 7-8) by the end of the project, and will be tested, validated and demonstrated in real conditions in Atlantic and Mediterranean countries, namely Portugal (PT), United Kingdom (UK), Spain (ES), Italy (IT), Croatia (HR) and Malta (MT). NETTAG+'s ambition is to change the paradigm of the fisheries industry, aspiring to transform the societal perspectives about the role of fishers as Guardians and Cleaners of the Ocean. NETTAG+ will empower the sector to take effective actions to address marine pollution, promoting their role as key actors to tackle marine pollution.

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Executive Summary

During the EU NETTAG+ project, six clean-up events were organised by project partners across five countries. Across these actions, a total of 1,478 kg of highly diverse marine litter was collected, reflecting both land-based and sea-based sources of pollution. Recovered items included everyday domestic waste such as plastic food packaging, cigarette butts, plastic fragments, bottle caps, glass bottles, aluminium cans, foam boxes, polystyrene, and other household objects. In addition, a significant proportion of fishing- and maritime-related debris was retrieved, including ropes, fishing lines, fishing nets, fishing traps, octopus pots, and other gear. The clean-ups also uncovered large and unusual items, such as a plastic chair, long tubing, firework debris, and even a streetlight, highlighting the variety and scale of materials entering marine and coastal environments.

The events engaged a diverse range of participants across different age groups, including local fishers, divers, students, teachers, chefs, and members of local communities. They provided a valuable opportunity for participants to gain first-hand experience of the scale of marine litter and increased their motivation to adopt environmentally responsible behaviours in their daily lives.

Here is an overview of the six clean up events organised:

Place/Country	Date	Kg of waste collected
Póvoa de Varzim, Portugal	08/06/2024	180 kg
Marsaskala, Malta	09/01/2025	50Kg
Tribunj, Croatia	22/05/2025	675 kg
Skradin, Croatia	18/03/2026	193 kg
Spadafora, Sicily, Italy	24/07/2025	350kg
Bueu, Spain	16/06/2025	30 Kg

1 Clean up events

This chapter presents an overview of the public beach and sea-bottom clean-up events implemented between June 2024 and March 2026 within the framework of the NETTAG+ project. The activities were organised by project partners across five countries—Portugal, Spain, Malta, Croatia, and Italy—as part of a coordinated effort to address marine litter and abandoned, lost and discarded fishing gear (ALDFG).

The clean-up events were designed as public actions, combining environmental remediation with public engagement and awareness-raising. Beach and sea-bottom clean-ups were organised in each participating country, involving a wide range of stakeholders including local fishers, recreational divers, schoolchildren, educators, and members of the general public.

These activities aimed to increase local awareness of the extent and diversity of marine litter, while encouraging more responsible consumption behaviours and improved waste management practices. By providing hands-on experience and direct exposure to marine pollution, the events fostered community involvement, strengthened cooperation between fisheries stakeholders and civil society, and reinforced shared responsibility for the protection of marine and coastal ecosystems.

1.1 Portugal

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On June 8, 2024, in celebration of World Oceans Day, the fishing community of Vila do Conde and Póvoa de Varzim in Portugal came together for a beach clean-up event titled “The Sea is Also Cleaned by Us!”. Organised by APMSHM, a partner of the NETTAG+ project, this initiative aimed to raise awareness about marine litter and highlight the crucial role fishers play in collecting and properly disposing of marine debris.

Around 70 volunteers, including fishers and their families spanning multiple generations, cleaned Praia do Peixe in Póvoa de Varzim and Prainha beach in Vila do Conde. Equipped with two bags each – one for recyclables (yellow bag) and one for general waste (white bag) – the participants worked diligently to clean “their” beaches.

Over 180 kg of litter were collected, including different domestic items (e.g., plastic food packaging, glass bottles, foam boxes), but also several maritime ropes, fishing nets, octopus pots, a 5-meter tube and even a streetlight. A big effort that was well rewarded with a delicious lunch prepared by the fishers and live music, fostering a sense of community and shared purpose.

The event was promoted on the NETTAG+ website ([here](#)) and social media and was covered by local media.

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Article in the Portuguese media reporting the event

1.2 Malta

©ARM

On 1 September 2025, a beach clean-up activity was successfully organised at St Thomas Bay, Marsaskala, bringing together 81 participants, including students and staff from Marsaskala St Joachim School summer school, STMC, and Carlo Diacono Middle and Secondary summer school. The event was organised by Aquatic Resources Malta (ARM) and combined environmental education with hands-on action and community engagement.

The activity began with an educational session introducing participants to the NETTAG+ project, an EU-funded initiative focused on reducing marine litter, with particular attention to abandoned, lost or discarded fishing gear. The session highlighted the impacts of marine pollution on ocean health, marine biodiversity, and coastal communities, while also underlining the role of sustainable fishing practices and citizen involvement in marine protection. The importance of beach clean-ups as awareness-raising tools and as a means of promoting responsible behaviour was also emphasised.

Following the briefing, participants took part in the clean-up activity, equipped with gloves, litter pickers and waste collection bags. Students, teachers and ARM officers worked together along the shoreline, **collecting over 50 kilograms of waste within a few hours**. The most commonly collected items included cigarette butts, plastic fragments, bottle caps, food packaging, fishing lines, small pieces of rope and other everyday items frequently found along the coast.

The hands-on experience allowed participants to gain a clearer understanding of the extent of marine litter and the pathways through which waste enters the marine environment, whether through accidental loss or careless disposal. Many participants expressed surprise at the volume of litter present and reported increased motivation to adopt environmentally responsible behaviours in their daily lives.

The event was promoted on the NETTAG+ website ([here](#)).

©ARM

1.3 Croatia

WWF Adria organised two cleanup and awareness-raising events aimed at addressing marine litter and abandoned, lost and discarded fishing gear (ALDFG). The activities took place in May 2025 at the Fishing Port of Tribunj and in March 2026 in Skradin, Croatia, and combined field operations, stakeholder engagement, and public outreach.

Fishing Port of Tribunj – May 2025

©WWF-Adria

The first event, held in May 2025 at the Fishing Port of Tribunj, **brought together over 60 volunteers**, including divers, local fishers, and members and employees of the Adria Fishing Cooperative, as well as representatives of local institutions and civil society. Participating organisations included LAG “More 249”, the Vodice and Tribunj Volunteer Fire Departments, Carretta Carretta Association, Mjesno poduzeće d.o.o. Tribunj, the Municipality and Tourist Board of Tribunj, and Sunce Organization.

Cleanup activities resulted in the removal of 675 kg of waste, equivalent to approximately 7 m³, from the fishing port and the nearby Sv. Nikola pier. A structured waste monitoring exercise was conducted

by students from the Maritime School of Split, under the supervision of Sunce Organization experts and academic staff, enabling systematic data collection to support long-term research on marine litter.

The event also included a panel discussion entitled “Passive Catch, Active Responsibility: Policy and Practice in Fisheries”, organised within the FishNoWaste project led by Sunce Organization. The panel brought together representatives from fisheries administration, the scientific community, environmental NGOs, and industry initiatives, highlighting the importance of coordinated action across sectors to address marine litter effectively.

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Skradin – March 2026

The second event took place on 18 March 2026, in connection with Global Recycling Day, in Skradin, near the estuary of the Krka River and adjacent to Krka National Park. Field activities were carried out at Prokljan Lake, a biodiverse estuarine system, in cooperation with local fishers, divers, and project partners.

The operation focused specifically on ghost gear removal. **Participants recovered 193 kg of debris**, including four fishing nets, three fishing traps, and additional debris, including a plastic chair and assorted marine litter, highlighting the persistence of lost fishing gear in underwater environments.

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In parallel, an environmental education activity was organised at the Skradin kindergarten, introducing children to marine biodiversity, recycling, and the impacts of ghost gear through interactive and creative approaches. The day concluded with a public session at the local Cultural Centre, presenting NETTAG+ objectives and related actions implemented with fishers and coastal communities across the Mediterranean and Atlantic regions.

Together, the two events demonstrated the effectiveness of integrating practical cleanup actions, stakeholder cooperation, data collection, and environmental education. These activities contributed tangible environmental benefits while reinforcing multi-stakeholder collaboration and shared responsibility for protecting marine ecosystems and promoting sustainable fisheries under the NETTAG+ project.

The events were promoted on the NETTAG+ website ([here](#) and [here](#)).

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1.4 Italy

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On 24 July 2025, WWF Italy and the EU-funded NETTAG+ project participated in the annual Festa del Mare (“Festival of the Sea”) in Spadafora, Sicily, organised by the local Pro Loco. **The event attracted over 2,000 participants** and served as a platform to raise awareness on plastic pollution, sustainable fisheries, and marine ecosystem protection, engaging fishers, scientists, citizens, and environmental organisations.

The programme included a beach clean-up activity coordinated by the NETTAG+ team, with the participation of more than 30 volunteers and local residents. **The action resulted in the collection of nearly 300 kg of marine litter**, including plastic items, discarded fishing gear, glass bottles, aluminium cans, polystyrene fragments, and firework debris, highlighting the scale of coastal plastic pollution.

In the afternoon, a public forum on sustainable fishing and responsible value chains engaged over 100 participants. The discussion involved local fishers, researchers from the University of Catania and the Anton Dohrn Zoological Station, restaurant owners, and WWF Italy representatives, emphasising the role of small-scale fisheries in supporting marine health and local economies. The event concluded with a photo exhibition on small-scale fisheries and a screening of the WWF documentary

MAREDDOLCE, illustrating how fishers are adapting to environmental challenges while preserving traditional livelihoods.

The events was promoted on the NETTAG+ website ([here](#)).

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1.5 Spain

©ARVI

On 16 June 2025, a clean-up of Pescadoira Beach in Bueu (Pontevedra, Spain) was carried out within the framework of the NETTAG+ project, with the aim of raising awareness among young people about marine litter issues.

In cooperation with the San Martiño Fishermen’s Guild of Bueu and the Vertidos Cero Association, a group of 40 schoolchildren from the Virxe Milagrosa School took part in the activity. During the clean-up, a total of 30 kg of litter, mainly plastic and wood, was collected from the beach.

Before and after the clean-up, participating students received briefings from marine-litter experts from the NETTAG+ project and the Vertidos Cero Association. These sessions provided guidance on how to carry out the beach clean-up and facilitated discussion on the issue of marine litter based on the items collected, including their likely sources and possible measures to prevent marine pollution.

As part of the programme, the students also visited Bueu’s fish market, where they received an introduction to its operation and to the role of the local fishermen’s guild. Additional environmental education activities were organised on the beach throughout the day, reinforcing the learning experience.